

WIRELESS MAGNETIC DATA TRANSFER TECHNIQUE

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Introduction

We usually use different mediums to send signals, for example, we transmit signals through light wave, sound wave and electromagnetic wave. And we transfer signals to any one of those mediums and the signal there means that there can be any kind of signal. In the modern days computers or different types of electronic devices communicate among themselves in different types of wireless mediums and among them, wireless magnetic data transfer is important things that I am going to discuss here.

What is wireless magnetic data transfer technique?

Wireless data transfer technique is a method for transferring data through variable magnetic field and data also be received by detecting that variable magnetic field which is created by sender position, here data will be modulate in that magnetic field.

We use the induction coil for generate magnetic field:

Practically we can make variable magnetic field using induction coil and induction coil is a thing that can convert electric energy to magnetic energy. If the electric signal as like an AC signal and so, the generated magnetic field also like a variable magnetic field or magnetic signal,

Mutual induction:

We use mutual induction for catch magnetic signal on secondary induction coil by concept of two coils mutual induction

If the coefficients of the two coils are L1 and L2 then the mutual induction coefficient is,

$$M = k\sqrt{L_1L_2}$$

Here k is a connection constant with 1 or less.

Now modern days for increase self-inductance of an induction coil we use a new diagram of induction coil as like as flowing diagram

Signal transferring technique:

We have all know that electrical signal is two type digital signal and analog signal, the digital signal carry digital data on of any modern electronic device and analog signal carry analog data.

Digital signal

Analog signal

Block diagram of wireless magnetic data transfer technique:

According to this diagram we have two devices here One is Sender Device another is Receiver Device and they are communicating through a variable magnetic field. In Sender side input signal is encoding by Signal Encoder than sender covert that electric signal to magnetic signal by sender coil.

In receiver device Receiver coil inducted by Sender coil and collect the magnetic signal for convert to Electric signal as analog, after that convert the analog signal to digital, Then Signal decoder decode the signal and give final output.

Here we have a problem in here, if we want to send any digital signal through an induction coil then the digital signal converted into analog signal.

So, after that when we collect that signal in receiver coil, then we need to change the analog signal to digital in proper way, so that the data in the signal is not lost.

Circuit diagram of wireless magnetic data transfer

How to we convert analog to digital signal in receiver device:

After receiving the signal, we used a comparator in circuit to convert analog signal to digital signal, here we give some following results for clearly understand how to works the circuit,

A

B

Here we can see two results here, graph A shows after sending the signal structure and if we direct push that Digital signal on sender coil then the B graph shows actual V-T characteristics (A and B is oscilloscope's graph of an electrical signal shows how the signal changes over time).

C

In diagram C we can see V-T characteristics of sender and receiver coil. After receiving the signal, comparator make it digital signal to properly use it.

It will be more accurate if we make sinewave analog signal from sender's digital signal, then we get more accuracy in receiver side.

Sender

Receiver

Output

Data sending-receiving protocols:

Data sending and receiving protocols is a rule of patterns, which is designed for communicate between two devices, it's give a proper way to organize and manages signals bit in a condition which have no probability of missing information, Cancel all garbage value, get input/output in proper way and if connection loss then next data packed will be send next process when get connect.

Serial wireless communication helps to transfer the data wirelessly, without any physical contact with the device that receives. Some of the wireless devices are Wi-Fi, Zigbee, Thread, MQTT, Bluetooth, RF, Lo-Ra, GPRS, NFC etc. they use some protocols for communicate two devices.

(For wireless magnetic data transfer technique, Data sending-receiving protocols I am not discussing here for word limitation of this content and it is under development mode)

Conclusion:

Wireless data transfer technique is a method for transferring data through variable magnetic field and data also be received by detecting that variable magnetic field which is created by sender position, here data will be modulate in that magnetic field. Now modern days many companies use this technique use in wireless charging device for send and receiving data, recent Apple iPhone is using this technique.

Reference:

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